

IPBES Data Management Tutorials

Chapter 1: Introduction to IPBES data management tutorials

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Description of Chapter

This chapter provides an overview on data management within the IPBES platform, and the series of the tutorials prepared by the task force on knowledge and data that will assist experts with the implementation of the IPBES data management policy.

Overview of Sessions:

- *Session 1.1. Welcome remarks*
 - Introduces the data management tutorials series and places it within the wider IPBES context.
 - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4018673](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4018673)

- *Session 1.2. Introduction to IPBES tutorials and training*
 - Provides a short introduction detailing the objectives of these tutorials and the responsibilities of the IPBES secretariat regarding data management.
 - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4014804](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014804)

- *Session 1.3. IPBES and data management*
 - Briefly covers how data management is involved in and influences each objective of the IPBES platform.
 - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4018578](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4018578)

- *Session 1.4. Introduction to the IPBES data management tutorials*
 - Summarizes the purpose of the data management tutorials, what they cover, and where to find transcripts and documentation.
 - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4014814](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014814)

Suggested citation:

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